

4,4'-Bis-5-Pyrazolones and Their 4,4'-Unsaturated Products for Possible Use as Fungicides

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4,4'-Bis-2-pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared by condensing 3-methyl-4-bromo-5-pyrazolones with 2-pyrazolin-5-ones or its 4-nitroso derivatives. Some of these bis-derivatives were converted into C_{4,4'} unsaturated compounds. All these compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Most of the compounds exhibit significant fungicidal activity and are comparable with the standard fungicides like *o*-Ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphoro dithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP and Derosal 60% WP.

IN continuation of our earlier work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁸ containing the 5-pyrazolone ring, it was considered of interest to study the fungitoxicity of the 4,4'-bis compounds obtained by joining two active 5-pyrazolone nuclei and corresponding C_{4,4'} unsaturated (-C₄=C₄-) derivatives. This has been accomplished by condensing 5-pyrazolone with 4-bromo-5-pyrazolone so as to obtain the bis-compound in which the two nuclei are linked together at C_{4,4'} position by a single bond. The formation of the bis-compound (A) was confirmed by comparing it with the bis-compound prepared by the standard method⁹, which involves refluxing of 5-pyrazolone with phenyl hydrazine.

The standard method could not be applied for the fusion of two dissimilar pyrazolone nuclei but this has been accomplished by adopting our present method.

It has also been reported by us¹ that introduction of a nitroso group at 4-position of 5-pyrazolone ring enhances the fungicidal activity considerably against the pathogens *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. So it was thought worthwhile to introduce a nitroso group into one of the two pyrazolone nuclei of the bis-compound. This has been achieved by condensing 4-bromo-5-pyrazolone with the 4-nitroso derivative of 5-pyrazolone.

Oxidation of the bis-compound in which -CH-CH- linkage at C_{4,4'} position was turned into -C=C- was done with a view to study and compare the fungitoxicity of the oxidation products with that of the parent bis-compound. The alkaline solution of the bis-compound was treated with a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide to produce the oxidation product¹⁰. This oxidation was also done by treating the bis-compound with nitric acid. The stereoisomerism of these 4,4'-bis-saturated and unsaturated pyrazolones was not investigated.

These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against the pathogens *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* following the standard method¹¹. All the compounds (Tables 1 and 2) exhibited pronounced fungicidal activity against *P. oryzae*. Bis-compounds (1, 5, 6, 8 and 14) and C₄-nitroso bis-compounds (17, 20 and 24) showed 100% spore germination inhibition against *P. oryzae*. All these compounds except 1 and 9 were active against *H. oryzae* and one C₄-nitroso compound (17) showed 100% germination inhibition against *H. oryzae*. Fungitoxicity against both the pathogens was not marked for the oxidation products (Table 3) except for compound (33) which exhibited 78% germination inhibition against *P. oryzae* only.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Nature of R''	M.P. °C	% Germination inhibition at 1000 ppm conc. <i>P. oryzae</i> <i>H. oryzae</i>	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	320(d)	100	55
2.	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	306	95	70
3.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	C ₆ H ₅	225	96	68
4.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₅	216	99	74
5.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₃ (2,4-)	C ₆ H ₅	173	100	62
6.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	CH ₃	185	100	68
7.	C ₆ H ₅	CONH ₂	CH ₃	305	85	65
8.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (NH ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	CH ₃	212	100	68
9.	H	H	CH ₃	323(d)	88	35
10.	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	306	94	70
11.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	C ₆ H ₅	282	78	62
12.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	333	92	65
13.	H	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	C ₆ H ₅	230	92	76
14.	H	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	CH ₃	148	100	88
15.	H	CONH ₂	CH ₃	261	62	63
16.	H	C ₆ H ₃ (NH ₂) ₂	CH ₃	180	79	60

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Nature of R''	M.P. °C	% Germination inhibition at 1000 ppm conc. <i>P. oryzae</i> <i>H. oryzae</i>	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	184	100	100
18.	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	188	89	67
19.	C ₆ H ₅	CONH ₂	CH ₃	179	68	60
20.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	186	100	62
21.	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	210	88	67
22.	H	H	CH ₃	above 350	79	60
23.	H	CONH ₂	CH ₃	above 350	89	74
24.	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	197	100	60

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Nature of R''	M.P. °C	% Germination inhibition at 1000 ppm conc. <i>P. oryzae</i> <i>H. oryzae</i>	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	230	72	56
26.	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	199	45	40

(Table 3 Contd.)

27.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	C ₆ H ₅	160	64	60
28.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₅	203	64	52
29.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	C ₆ H ₅	144	60	49
30.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	CH ₃	148	60	46
31.	C ₆ H ₅	CONH ₂	CH ₃	228	52	46
32.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (NH ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	CH ₃	196	60	54
33.	H	H	CH ₃	225	78	55
34.	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	199	45	40
35.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	C ₆ H ₅	186	61	50
36.	H	C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ (2,4-)	C ₆ H ₅	195	68	54

It was noted that compounds (1-6, 8-10, 13, 14, 17, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24) inhibited spore germination in the same range as the standard fungicides like *o*-Ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphoro dithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP and Derosal 6% WP; thus these may prove as promising fungicides. In conclusion, it is found that introduction of a C₄-nitroso group enhances the fungicidal activity whilst the activity considerably decreases when a C₄=C_{4'} double bond is introduced into the *bis*-derivatives.

Experimental

4, 4'-Bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) :

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1 g), 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-bromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1 g) and fused sodium acetate (1 g) were taken in ethanol (5 ml). The resulting mixture was refluxed over a water bath for 2 hrs. The alcohol was then boiled off and distilled water (10 ml) was added. It was allowed to stand for 2 hrs. A white compound separated out which was filtered and dried. On crystallisation from ethanol, it yielded white coloured crystals, m.p. 320°(d), yield 80%.

The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide and gives colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

$$\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}} 1595, 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}.$$

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-4'-nitroso-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one-4'-yl)-5-one :

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1 g) was taken along with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-bromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1.2 g) and fused sodium acetate (1 g) in ethanol (5 ml). The resulting mixture was refluxed over a water bath for 2 hrs. The alcohol was then boiled off and distilled water (10 ml) was added to it. The whole solution was allowed to stand for 2 hrs. A yellowish brown coloured compound was obtained. On crystallisation from ethanol, it yielded yellowish brown crystals, m.p. 184°, yield 80%.

The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide and gives colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

$$\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}} 1715, 1590, 1540 \text{ cm}^{-1}.$$

C₄₄, unsaturated product of 4, 4'-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) :

To 4, 4'-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) (1 g) was added (1 : 1) HNO₃ (5 ml). Immediately a blue pasty mass was produced which was converted into blue solid after a few minutes. The compound was filtered, washed with 10% sodium hydroxide and dried. On crystallisation from acetone, it produced blue crystals, m.p. 230°, yield 80%.

The same compound was also obtained by using iodine in potassium iodide¹⁰.

The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide and gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1695, 1590, 1280, 980 cm⁻¹.

$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 206^{nm} <(log t=4.6749),

246^{nm} <(log t=4.5794)

NMR (CCl₄) : δ 2.03(S, 3H), 2.43(S, 3H),

The fungicidal data of the synthesised compounds are listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3. The compounds (1, 9, 25, 33) are already reported in literature. All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

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